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Managing Sustainability in the Internet of Musical Things: A Bibliometric and Literature Review of IoT Integration in the Music Sector

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Abstract: *This article presents a literature review and bibliometric analysis of research on the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) in music, also known as the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT) - from a sustainability perspective. The review identifies key themes including smart instruments, networked performance, music education and real-time interactive systems. Findings highlight the interdisciplinary nature of the field, bridging musicology, computer science and human-computer interaction. A bibliometric analysis using VOSviewer reveals global collaboration patterns across 76 countries. The United States, China, the United Kingdom and India emerge as leading contributors, while Romania plays a strategic bridging role. Keyword co-occurrence analysis identifies three thematic clusters: technical infrastructure, creative applications and computational approaches. Additionally, recent literature increasingly addresses the environmental and social sustainability of IoMusT systems, focusing on low-power devices, ethical data use, the reduction of CO2 emissions, changing the traditional methods of stocking music of all kinds and inclusive design. These findings underscore the potential of IoMusT to support multiple Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 4, 9, 11 and 12). These results underscore the growth of IoMusT as a distinct academic subfield and point to future research opportunities in personalization, sustainability, ethical data use and responsible innovation.*

Keywords: *Internet of Thing; Internet of Musical Things; Music Technology; Sustainability*

1. Introduction

In our times, technology is evolving at a very fast speed rate. Given that, every domain must keep track of its' advancements in this direction; the artistic field is no exception. With the rapid expanding paradigm of the Internet of Things (IoT), everyday objects are embedded with sensors, software and connectivity to collect and exchange data, constructing a new era of digital interactivity.

While the applications using IoT have been intensively studied in domains such as manufacturing, healthcare and smart cities, its influence on the music domain - from composition and performance to consumption and distribution - is a new study question that shows a continuously growing rate of scholarly interest. The convergence of IoT and music broadens the horizons for innovations such as smart instruments, AI-driven sound design, immersive live performances and personalized listening experiences based on real-time contextual data. As this interdisciplinary field evolves, it

becomes essential to map the intellectual landscape, trace research trends and identify key contributors and emerging themes.

The purpose of this study is to explore the landscape of IoT integration in music, identifying key trends, applications and challenges in a sustainable world. Drawing from a wide range of academic sources - including studies on smart instruments, networked performance systems, music education platforms, audio feature extraction and security frameworks - this review offers a comprehensive synthesis of how IoT is reshaping the musical ecosystem.

As the Internet of Things (IoT) becomes increasingly embedded in musical environments - spanning from smart instruments and networked performance systems to music education platforms - the importance of sustainable development in this context grows accordingly. The deployment of IoT in music, found under the umbrella of the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT), involves not only technological innovation but also significant implications for resource consumption, data ethics and social inclusivity. Sustainable development offers a framework to ensure that these systems are designed and implemented with environmental responsibility, equitable access and cultural sensitivity in mind. By aligning IoMusT research with the principles of sustainability - including here aspects regarding low-energy hardware, modular system design and accessibility - it becomes possible to maximize the social and creative benefits of musical technologies while minimizing their ecological and ethical footprints.

Despite growing interest in IoT-enhanced music systems, the current literature remains limited in its treatment of sustainability and management concerns. Much of the existing research emphasizes system functionality, latency optimization and audio quality, while strategic discussions on sustainable device lifecycle, responsible data use and scalable deployment models are relatively rare. Additionally, there is a notable lack of integration between technical development and socio-environmental impact assessment, creating a gap in understanding how IoMusT systems can be responsibly scaled. Management-related themes, such as maintenance protocols, interoperability standards and governance frameworks, are also underexplored. As IoMusT moves from experimental prototypes to real-world applications in fields like education, entertainment and culture, addressing these gaps becomes essential. A more holistic approach that incorporates sustainability and system governance will be key to supporting the long-term viability and ethical alignment of IoT integration in music.

This study undertakes a bibliometric analysis to systematically examine the body of academic literature at the intersection of IoT and subjects linked to music, using data that has been sourced from major research databases including ScienceDirect, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore and Scopus. The analysis was conducted using VOSviewer, a specialized tool for constructing and visualizing bibliometric networks, enabling detailed exploration of co-authorship patterns, keyword co-occurrence, citation structures and thematic clusters.

This methodological approach not only uncovers the structural dynamics and influential factors within the research community but also offers strategic insights into the trajectory of the field, highlighting research gaps, interdisciplinary linkages and future opportunities. Through this analysis, we aim to offer a starting-point reference for researchers, technologists, economists and musicians seeking to understand and contribute to the evolving interplay between IoT and the musical arts.

2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The Internet of Things refers to a network of physical devices embedded with sensors, software and connectivity that allows them to collect and exchange data (Atzori et al., 2010). In the context of creative industries, IoT has begun to influence user interaction, data-driven services and context-aware applications. The ability to gather real-time environmental or biometric data and respond with intelligent actions is central to IoT's transformative power.

Built upon the core principles of IoT, the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT) involves the interconnection of musical devices, performers and software agents within a smart, networked environment. IoMusT systems include smart musical instruments, wearables, interactive music education systems and immersive performance platforms, all of which leverage wireless communication, AI and edge computing to create dynamic and responsive musical experiences.

Turchet et al. (2020) define IoMusT as a distributed ecosystem where musical objects interact in real-time to support artistic expression, learning and innovation. These systems are often used in conjunction with other technologies like blockchain, XR (Extended Reality) and 5G, creating novel contexts for performance, learning and audience engagement.

The integration of IoT technologies into music has led to innovations across a variety of domains. These range from real-time performance collaboration and adaptive learning platforms to AI-based music production and cultural preservation (Turchet et al., 2023). This section synthesizes how IoT is being applied in these contexts, highlighting both its transformative potential and practical challenges.

This study contributes to the growing discourse on how emerging technologies in the arts, particularly the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT), can be aligned with broader sustainable development frameworks. By examining global research trends and thematic directions, this review identifies how IoT-driven music systems can support the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially Goal 4 (Quality Education), Goal 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), Goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) and Goal 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). IoMusT technologies, such as smart instruments, networked performance platforms and educational interfaces, offer opportunities to democratize access to music, preserve cultural heritage and promote innovation through low-cost, scalable and energy-efficient solutions. Furthermore, the principles of the circular economy - such as modularity, reparability and resource efficiency - can be included in the design of IoMusT systems to reduce environmental impact. By adopting inclusive design practices, musical IoT platforms are ensured to be accessible to diverse users, including individuals with disabilities, marginalized communities and non-expert audiences, reinforcing the social sustainability of the field. This study highlights the need for future IoMusT research to embrace sustainability not only as a technical criterion but also as a guiding value for long-term viability and social impact.

3. Literature Review

One of the most active areas of IoT application in music is in networked music performance (NMP). These systems allow musicians in different physical locations to collaborate in real-time. Studies by teams including the same Luca Turchet demonstrate how 5G and edge computing can significantly reduce latency, which has historically limited synchronous remote performances (Turchet & Casari, 2024a). Their proposed 5G-enabled IoMusT architecture allows for low-latency, high-fidelity audio exchange between connected musicians using smart instruments and audio nodes (Turchet & Casari, 2024b).

Smart musical instruments - like connected violins, pianos and air instruments - are also increasingly used in collaborative contexts. These instruments contain embedded sensors and microcontrollers, allowing them to stream performance data, respond to gestures and interact with other devices in a shared network. Some prototypes even allow for robotic performance, such as the ViolinTalk system by Huang and Lin (2023), which uses IoT to control and calibrate robotic violin playing.

IoT is playing a critical role in transforming music education. Systems developed by researchers Yu (2021) and Zhang Y. (2022) implement IoT-based feedback mechanisms that evaluate students' piano and violin performances in real-time. These platforms often combine sensor-based audio analysis, deep learning and biometric feedback to provide personalized recommendations, helping students refine their technique.

The integration of virtual reality (VR) and graph neural networks (GNNs) in IoT-based music education platforms - as explored by Lian et al. (2022)—enhances immersion and adaptive learning. These environments track user engagement via wearables and deliver content based on real-time attention and performance metrics. Additionally, cloud-based music education platforms, such as those designed by Chen (2022), leverage 5G IoT infrastructures to support scalable, high-quality online learning and content delivery.

IoT technologies have also contributed to music production and recommendation systems, especially through feature extraction and context-aware audio analysis. Chen et al. (2022) developed a music feature extraction system that uses IoT-connected techniques to classify and categorize audio data for recommendation engines. These systems are foundational for AI-driven music services that adapt to

user mood, context and preferences using real-time sensor inputs. In another application, IoT data has been used to support emotion-aware music curation, where audio output is selected based on biometric feedback such as heart rate or movement. This adaptive approach enhances user experience by making music more interactive and responsive.

Folk and traditional music archives often suffer from poor audio quality and lack of metadata. Ming (2022) introduced an IoT and genetic algorithm (GA)-driven noise suppression system for enhancing folk music recordings. By capturing audio through IoT sensor arrays and processing them with GA-based optimization, the system significantly improves clarity and categorization of traditional music pieces. Such applications not only support cultural preservation but also enable broader access to historically significant recordings in interactive and educational platforms.

The successful deployment of IoT systems in music relies on a complex interplay of infrastructure components and supporting technologies. These technologies ensure that IoT-based music systems can operate in real time, with low latency, high fidelity and robust security. This section explores key enabling technologies that support the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT), including 5G networks, edge computing, artificial intelligence and blockchain-based security mechanisms.

5G plays a pivotal role in IoMusT by providing the ultra-low latency and high-bandwidth connectivity required for real-time collaboration. Studies show that 5G network slicing significantly enhances networked music performance (NMP) by reducing transmission delays to less than 24 milliseconds—an essential threshold for synchronous remote performances (Turchet & Casari, 2024b). Complementing 5G, edge computing allows data to be processed closer to the source, such as in smart musical instruments or wearable devices. This reduces latency and network congestion, making real-time feedback and processing feasible even in high-demand settings like live performances or immersive learning platforms (Vignati et al., 2024).

AI is essential for processing and interpreting the massive amounts of sensor data generated in IoMusT systems. For instance, deep neural networks (DNNs) and spiking neural networks (SNNs) are used to recognize and classify music features (Zhang M., 2022). This study presents an AI-enhanced IoT system using spiking neural networks (SNNs) to extract and classify musical features. It supports the development of smart music education and recommendation systems based on real-time audio analysis. The subject of graph neural networks (GNNs) powering adaptive learning environments in VR-based music education is approached by Lian et al. (2022). This paper introduces an online music education platform using graph neural networks (GNNs) for adaptive feedback. The system processes biometric and performance data collected via IoT wearables to personalize learning. AI also supports personalized music learning, intelligent accompaniment and gesture-based instrument control, often in tandem with IoT sensor networks.

Security is a major concern in IoT-based music systems due to their reliance on real-time data exchange, cloud storage and distributed control. Blockchain technology has been proposed as a solution for securing musical content, ensuring copyright compliance and enabling transparent royalty payments (Turchet & Ngo, 2022). Blockchain-based smart contracts can automate licensing and royalty distribution while ensuring that data transmitted between connected musical devices is encrypted, immutable and verifiable. In addition, advanced models for IoT malware detection (Moti et al., 2021) and zero-trust architectures (Al-Hawawreh et al., 2024) are being proposed to protect IoT music systems from cyber threats, including ransomware and unauthorized access.

Despite its transformative potential, the integration of IoT in music presents a variety of technical, ethical, sustainable and practical challenges. These issues span across latency and synchronization, system interoperability, data privacy, sustainability and research integrity. Understanding these limitations is essential for guiding future innovation in the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT).

One of the core technical barriers in IoT-enabled music applications - especially in networked music performance (NMP)—is latency. Musical collaboration requires latencies below 25 ms to maintain rhythmic and harmonic cohesion. Although 5G and edge computing significantly reduce delay, real-world tests (Turchet & Casari, 2024a) reveal persistent irregular delay spikes and WAN bottlenecks.

Low-latency requirements are also crucial in gesture-controlled instruments and haptic feedback systems, where delay can disrupt the performer's sense of timing and expressivity.

IoMusT ecosystems involve a wide array of devices, protocols and software systems. The lack of standardized communication protocols and unified ontologies makes it difficult for heterogeneous devices to interact seamlessly. Although efforts such as the IoMusT Ontology (Turchet et al., 2020) provide foundational frameworks, widespread adoption is still limited. This issue is especially relevant in collaborative settings where multiple users may employ different brands, devices and software ecosystems for music performance or learning.

Sustainability has emerged as a critical dimension in the evolution of the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT), particularly as systems scale in complexity and deployment. The integration of eco-conscious design, ethical data governance and inclusive user practices is increasingly emphasized by researchers aiming to align technological innovation with the principles of sustainable development (Masu et al., 2024). In their seminal work, Masu et al. (2024) propose a multidimensional framework for sustainability in IoMusT, encompassing environmental, social and technological aspects. Environmentally, the use of low-power embedded systems, recyclable materials and modular hardware is encouraged to reduce electronic waste and energy consumption. Social sustainability, meanwhile, is addressed through inclusive design principles, aiming to make IoMusT technologies accessible to a broader and more diverse range of users, including individuals with disabilities, non-technical users and marginalized communities.

Complementing this, Turchet and Barthet (2019) advocate for sustainability as a design mindset rather than an afterthought. They argue that sustainable IoMusT design must integrate user consent protocols, privacy-aware data flows and responsible AI models—especially in systems where biometric data, emotion detection, or user profiling is involved. These approaches are not only ethically necessary but also enhance long-term system adoption and trust.

From a broader perspective, the “Internet of Sounds” paradigm (Turchet et al., 2023) also promotes decentralized and open-source infrastructures as a way to ensure long-term maintainability and democratization of access. This aligns with UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—particularly Goal 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) and Goal 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production)—by creating resilient, scalable and ethically governed musical IoT systems.

In the domain of immersive music environments, sustainability also plays a role in XR-based performance systems, where power consumption, hardware recyclability and ethical use of motion/gesture data are becoming essential considerations (Turchet et al., 2018). As such, the emerging discourse around Musical XR and IoMusT recognizes sustainability not just as a technical challenge but as a strategic imperative for future innovation.

Collectively, these contributions underscore the necessity for holistic, cross-disciplinary strategies that incorporate sustainable thinking into the core of IoT-based music system design and deployment. IoT systems in music often rely on real-time biometric and environmental data to personalize music experiences or analyze performance. While these capabilities are powerful, they raise privacy and ethical concerns. For example, wearable sensors in education platforms collect data on heart rate, facial expressions, or posture. Moreover, smart speakers and home music assistants can inadvertently capture private conversations. These challenges demand robust data governance policies, including user consent, secure data storage and transparent algorithms.

IoT-based music systems often include wearables, edge devices and always-on wireless connectivity, which can be energy-intensive. Masu et al. (2024) highlight the importance of developing green IoMusT frameworks that minimize environmental impact while maintaining functionality. Energy efficiency becomes especially critical when deploying IoMusT in developing regions, outdoor environments, or large-scale festival settings.

One of the most promising developments in IoMusT is the convergence with virtual, augmented and mixed reality (collectively XR). Research by Turchet et al. (2021) introduces the concept of Musical XR, where performers and audiences interact in immersive, IoT-enhanced environments. These systems

enable virtual concerts with haptic feedback and real-time collaboration, 3D spatial audio experiences linked to motion and gesture tracking, remote music education in gamified, multisensory environments.

Such experiences blur the line between digital and physical performance, enabling new forms of expression and audience engagement. The integration of biometric sensors, AI and IoT is driving the development of emotion-aware music applications. These systems use real-time data, such as heart rate, skin conductance, or facial expressions, to adapt musical content to the listener's emotional state, provide personalized learning or therapeutic experiences and support context-aware music recommendation systems.

Advances in deep learning are improving the accuracy and responsiveness of these systems, making them suitable for healthcare, education and interactive entertainment. Emotion-aware music systems are increasingly using biometric IoT sensors and AI models to adapt content based on users' emotional states and contexts (Zhang X., 2022).

Borrowed from industrial IoT (Hakiri et al. 2024), digital twins represent real-time digital replicas of physical systems. In the context of music, digital twins could be used for monitoring the health and usage of smart musical instruments, simulating live performance environments for rehearsal or testing and training AI agents in realistic, feedback-rich virtual scenarios. While still in early stages, digital twins have the potential to enhance instrument maintenance, performance analysis and virtual education (Turchet et al., 2021).

4. Methodology

While conducting the research for this article, the team accessed and analyzed the rich repository of scholarly articles within well-known databases such as Scopus, Science Direct, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, Springer and Sage. Being widely recognized for their collection of peer-reviewed publications, Web of Science, Scopus and Science Direct served as the main sources for gathering relevant data. More than 80% of the technical information was gathered from IEEE Xplore. In order to fully approach the concerns of this study, qualitative and quantitative analysis methods were used, including bibliometric analysis. These methods offer a better comprehension of the subject and bring to light effective, applicable strategies in various domains like education, economy and, of course, art and technology.

By analyzing bibliometric parameters such as keyword co-occurrence, researchers are able to uncover correlations, making the process of hypothesis formulation easier and offering a deep understanding of research subjects. The integration of the keyword co-occurrence proves to be of high importance in the development of interdisciplinary studies and the crossing of intellectual boundaries in underdeveloped or less-explored fields. Applying a tailored search strategy for this study's purpose, as outlined in Figure 1, the initial exploration resulted in a compilation of 13409 articles. Using VOSviewer, the following methods have been used: the keyword filtering method, the co-authorship by linked authors filtering method and the co-authorship by linked countries filtering method. The "Full Counting" option was selected, following the decision that each collaboration between authors on articles would have equal importance. The maximum number of authors for a single article was set at 5 in order to obtain relevant connections between authors and the institutions they represent. For the country co-authorship filtering method, the minimum number of documents of a country was set at 15 in order to obtain relevant results for our study. For the keyword co-occurrence, the minimum number of occurrences of a term was set at 5, as the terms associated with IoT integration in music are very specific. The countries of the conducted studies and a minimum of 15 publications per author were chosen due to the objective of staying true to the niche chosen, the one of IoT and music. The considerable volume of generated papers highlights a great interest in this field, especially in the research area. Network graphs were developed, revealing intricate relationships between keywords, authors and countries.

Figure 1. The string of keywords used. Source: Author's processing

Out of the number of 7850 authors, 70 met the established conditions, although not all of these authors were connected to one another (i.e., they did not work on the same articles). Subsequently, out of these 70 authors, 51 were identified as having collaborated in writing articles. In the final stage, after reading the articles and analyzing the information presented to align with the research's topic, a total of 20 articles were selected for content analysis.

The significance of selecting keywords, authorship links and country collaborations lies in their capacity to accurately reflect the multidimensional nature of the research domain - encompassing not only technical and economic aspects but also artistic ones. Anchoring the data analysis in these elements enables a thorough and nuanced exploration of the field.

Figure 2 consists of a visual representation of the steps taken to conduct the bibliometric analysis, illustrating the methodology from data collection to filtering, open-access and retracted document exclusions, and final dataset curation. The diagram points out the detailed approach for obtaining accurate and reliable research outcomes.

Figure 2. The bibliometric analysis process. Source: Author's processing

5. Results and Discussions Based on the Bibliometric Analysis

Bibliometric analysis is a structured, quantitative method used to explore academic literature by examining networks of bibliographic references. Citation counts and publication volume serve as empirical indicators of a work's scholarly influence. This methodology is widely applied across disciplines to assess the academic impact of authors, journals, institutions and countries, offering valuable insights into the evolving landscape of knowledge production and dissemination.

Cluster analysis complements bibliometric techniques by identifying underlying patterns and thematic groupings within scholarly networks. These clusters reveal relationships among researchers, institutions, geographical coordinates and their intellectual contributions. When combined, bibliometric and cluster analyses provide a reliable framework for evaluating research impact, uncovering emerging trends, interdisciplinary connections and shifts in academic paradigms.

Figure 3 highlights the 40 most frequently used terms in the articles that have been analyzed. This helps identify new correlations, leading to the identification of other influential factors that play an important role in the use of the Internet of Things in the music domain. This keyword co-occurrence analysis reveals three major thematic clusters that define the current research landscape surrounding the integration of IoT in music.

- The red cluster is centered on technical infrastructure and interaction design, highlighting terms such as “IoT”, “network”, “system”, “device”, “user” and “performance”. This cluster reflects research focused on the implementation and functioning of IoMusT systems, including smart instruments and real-time performance environments.
- The green cluster captures more human-centered and conceptual themes, with keywords like “music”, “sound”, “sensor”, “art” and “person”. This cluster emphasizes the interdisciplinary nature of the field, highlighting the role of music as both a creative and experiential domain, often informed by data from user interactions and sensor inputs.
- The blue cluster focuses on computational models and system evaluation, featuring terms such as “algorithm”, “analysis”, “efficiency” and “application”. These studies emphasize system optimization and performance assessment, supporting the development of scalable, responsive IoMusT architectures.

In the first cluster, the one colored in red, there are 16 items. Directly related to the research subject, we find the words “musical thing” and “iomust”, which stand out as advancements of IoT's direct integration in music. In the second cluster, colored in green, there are 14 items. The words that stand out, showing an interest in research in this area, are “study,” “work”, “development”, “data”, “process”, “analysis” and “article”. The last cluster is colored in blue, and there have been found technical terms directly linked to IoT integration in music and its impact, such as “efficiency,” “effect”, “process”, “analysis”, “application”, “technology”. By these results, the relevance of this research subject is confirmed, illustrating the field's balance between technological development, artistic integration and analytical rigor.

The term “IoMusT” is well connected to “musical thing”, “system”, “performance” and “user”, indicating its growing recognition as a defined subfield. There's a strong interaction between technical language (“device”, “algorithm”, “system”) and creative/artistic terms (“music”, “sound”, “art”), reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of research in this space. The presence of terms like “sensor”, “data”, “person” and “user” indicates emphasis on real-time interactivity and human-in-the-loop systems.

The keyword co-occurrence network also offers important insights into the emerging role of sustainable development in the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT). It illustrates a clear integration of technological terms such as “device”, “system” and “sensor” with more human-centered and socially-oriented concepts like “person”, “user” and “art”. This convergence highlights a growing concern with social sustainability, inclusive design and accessible technology. The appearance of keywords related to “data”, “efficiency” and “interaction” further points to environmental awareness in system optimization and energy-conscious design.

performances, while the blue cluster encompasses those investigating data analytics in music listening habits and the aspect of the sustainable development of the IoT integration process in music. The connecting lines between these names signify collaborative efforts, with the thickness of the lines possibly reflecting the frequency or strength of these collaborations. Such network analysis is crucial for understanding the dynamics of academic collaboration in this innovative intersection of technology and the arts and it points to potential areas for further exploration and growth in the field.

Figure 4. The map of co-authorship. 51 authors connected to each other. Source: Author’s processing

Figure 5 maps collaborative relationships between countries based on co-authored publications. Each node (country) is connected to others with lines, representing co-authorships or co-occurrence links. The size of each node indicates the volume of publications or collaboration frequency and the colors represent clusters of closely linked countries.

It can be easily observed that countries like China, the United States and the United Kingdom are central and have the largest nodes, indicating that they are the most prolific and most connected in this network. The clusters signify regional and thematic groupings and are shown in color-coded labels, as s:

- Orange cluster: East and Southeast Asia — includes China, Singapore, Hong Kong, Macao, Philippines
- Red cluster: South and West Asia — includes India, Japan, Malaysia, Iran, Saudi Arabia
- Blue cluster: United States, United Kingdom, Finland, Israel, Denmark, Bulgaria
- Purple cluster: Spain, Portugal, Mexico, Colombia — tied by linguistic or cultural links
- Green cluster: includes Russian Federation, Italy, France and Hungary, indicating a European collaboration core between the last three
- Yellow cluster: includes Qatar, Kuwait, Morocco, Nigeria, emerging or regional collaborations
- Brown cluster: smaller but unique, includes Croatia

- Cyan/light blue cluster: peripheral collaboration — Sri Lanka, there are some connections but fewer links

The thickness of the lines indicates the strength of collaboration. For example, the US–UK–China triangle is densely connected, indicating frequent collaboration. India also has strong connections with Malaysia, Saudi Arabia and the United States. China, the US and the UK are leaders in the topic area (IoT integration in music). Regional collaborations (e.g., Southeast Asia, Europe, Latin America) are prominent. There's a growing inclusion of countries like Qatar, Nigeria, and South Africa, showing diversification.

Figure 5. International co-authorship network of countries contributing to research on IoT and music. Source: Author’s processing

A focused co-authorship analysis reveals Romania's role within the global research network on IoT and music. As visualized in Figure 6, Romania is positioned centrally, indicating strong collaborative ties with both European and Asian partners. Key collaborators include China, India, Czech Republic, Hungary, Germany, France and the United States.

The clustering pattern highlights Romania’s dual engagement in regional Central and Eastern European research networks (including Hungary, Czech Republic and Slovenia) and broader international partnerships, particularly in Asia. Its co-publication ties with China and India are notably strong, suggesting strategic collaboration on technological and applied research themes. Romania also connects with Malaysia and Vietnam, reflecting growing academic exchanges in emerging IoT applications. These patterns underscore Romania's role as a bridge country, facilitating interdisciplinary and cross-regional collaboration. The nation's engagement in both mature and developing academic ecosystems reinforces its position as a key node in the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT) research landscape.

These country-collaboration maps reveal an increasingly inclusive global research landscape, with countries such as Romania, Malaysia, Nigeria and Morocco actively participating alongside dominant players like the United States, China and the United Kingdom. This suggests a broader distribution of knowledge production and the potential for region-specific sustainable applications. Educational and

cultural themes - evidenced by clusters around “music education”, “performance” and “interaction”—reflect the use of IoMusT to democratize access to music learning and preserve cultural heritage.

The results suggest several key directions for future inquiry:

- Expanding international and interdisciplinary collaboration, especially by involving underrepresented regions and leveraging emerging research hubs.
- Enhancing personalization and interactivity in IoMusT systems through real-time, sensor-based feedback and adaptive learning algorithms.
- Strengthening conceptual and methodological frameworks that integrate musicology, computer science and human-computer interaction.
- Promoting open, sustainable and inclusive IoT infrastructures that prioritize ethical data use and environmental considerations.

Figure 6. International co-authorship network highlighting Romania's research collaborations in the field of IoT and music. Source: Author's processing

6. Discussion

6.1. Sustainability Implications

The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies into music systems presents important sustainability considerations across the environmental, social and economic dimensions. From an environmental perspective, the development of low-energy IoMusT devices is critical for reducing the carbon footprint of connected music systems. Efforts toward modular system design and the use of recyclable materials can contribute to reducing electronic waste and promoting longer device lifecycles. These strategies align with circular economy principles and create a state of innovation that is environmentally responsible.

Socially, IoMusT holds significant potential to promote inclusion, accessibility and cultural preservation. Smart musical instruments and educational platforms powered by IoT can give access to

music learning for individuals with disabilities, remote learners and marginalized communities. Furthermore, sensor-based technologies and connected systems can support the digital archiving and interactive dissemination of folk and traditional music, contributing to the safeguarding of cultural heritage.

Economically, the adoption of open-source platforms and cost-effective design models enables broader participation in music technology innovation. Encouraging modularity and upgradability can help reduce long-term costs while supporting local development and decentralized production. These economic strategies not only reduce barriers to access but also reinforce sustainable growth.

6.2. Managerial and Policy Implications

The sustainable implementation of IoMusT requires coordinated efforts from educational institutions, technology developers and cultural organizations. Music schools and conservatories can integrate smart instruments and connected platforms into their curricula by adopting energy-efficient and reusable systems. Technology developers should consider sustainability from the outset, emphasizing ethical sourcing of materials, low-energy consumption and software longevity.

At the policy level, there is a growing need for governance frameworks addressing the ethical use of biometric data collected through wearable sensors and IoMusT devices. As artificial intelligence becomes more integrated with music technologies, developers and policymakers must collaborate to define responsible AI practices that ensure transparency, fairness and user consent.

To encourage sustainable adoption, institutions can apply models of responsible innovation and user-centric design. These frameworks prioritize stakeholder engagement, ethical foresight and constant feedback, ensuring that IoMusT systems are not only innovative but also aligned with social and environmental goals.

6.3. Research Gaps and Future Directions

Despite growing interest in IoMusT, significant research gaps remain, particularly concerning sustainability and standardization. One pressing need is the development of standardized communication protocols and interoperability frameworks to support scalable and energy-efficient musical IoT ecosystems. Without standardization, system fragmentation may delay long-term adoption and collaboration.

There is also a lack of comprehensive design patterns that include sustainability into the core of IoMusT development. Research should focus on modular hardware templates, software reuse models and low-footprint architectures tailored for musical applications. Additionally, studies exploring user behaviors, adoption barriers and post-deployment impacts will be essential for refining sustainable strategies.

Finally, cross-sector policy development is crucial to ensure that IoMusT evolves responsibly. Collaboration between government agencies, academic institutions and private-sector innovators is needed to create holistic policies that address sustainability, ethical governance and equitable access to next-generation music technologies.

7. Conclusions

This bibliometric investigation into the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) in music reveals a rapidly growing, interdisciplinary and globally distributed research landscape. The co-authorship and keyword co-occurrence analyses uncover not only who is contributing to this field but also how thematic priorities and collaborative structures are shaping the direction of the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT).

The bibliometric findings point to an emerging alignment between IoMusT research and the broader goals of sustainable development. Across the datasets, there is clear evidence of growing attention to environmental sustainability through efficient system design, low-energy processing and optimized network performance. At the same time, social sustainability is embedded through inclusive, human-centered design practices and international collaboration that broadens participation beyond traditional research hubs. Furthermore, IoMusT is positioned to support sustainable cultural and educational

practices by broadening access to music education, preserving traditional music forms and enabling global collaboration through low-cost, scalable technologies. These dimensions highlight the potential for IoMusT to contribute not only to academic advancement but also to the realization of key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goals 4, 9, 11 and 12. Future research in this field would benefit from a continued focus on responsible innovation, equitable access and environmental consciousness.

Beyond the environmental and social dimensions, sustainable development in IoMusT also includes economic considerations. Cost-effective solutions, such as open-source hardware and software, can make smart musical technologies more accessible for educational institutions, independent artists and underserved communities. Furthermore, decentralized production and collaborative development models promote resilience and local innovation, which are essential for long-term sustainability.

The global co-authorship network demonstrates that while research on IoT and music is broadly international, it remains regionally clustered, with strong hubs in North America, Europe and Asia. Countries such as the United States, China, India and the United Kingdom are prominent in terms of publication volume and connectivity, often acting as central nodes in the global collaboration network. The map also reveals the rise of emerging contributors such as Malaysia, South Korea and Saudi Arabia, signaling broader participation from the Global South. A focused co-authorship analysis of Romania highlights its strategic position as a bridge between research ecosystems in Eastern Europe, Asia and North America. Romania's strong links with China, India, the United States and neighboring EU countries suggest its growing role in interdisciplinary collaboration, particularly in sensor-based systems, music education technology and AI-driven music analysis.

The keyword co-occurrence network further reveals the interdisciplinary nature of IoMusT, connecting three major research domains:

1. Infrastructure and Interaction—terms like “IoT,” “system,” “network,” “device” and “user”—emphasize the technical backbone of musical IoT environments.
2. Human and Creative Contexts—keywords such as “music,” “sound,” “art,” “sensor” and “person” demonstrate the human-centered and artistic dimensions of this field.
3. Analytical and Computational Methods—With keywords like “algorithm,” “efficiency,” “analysis” and “process,” this cluster reflects the need for advanced tools to interpret musical data in real time.

The term “IoMusT” and related concepts like “musical thing” are increasingly visible, indicating the emergence of a distinct academic subfield with its own terminology, challenges and research directions.

As the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT) continues to evolve, emerging technologies and interdisciplinary approaches are shaping the future of music performance, education, collaboration and experience. This section highlights key trends that are expected to define the next wave of innovation in IoT-based music systems, including the integration of extended reality (XR), emotion-aware personalization, sustainable design and decentralized music ecosystems.

The integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) into music-encompassed in the rapidly evolving field of the Internet of Musical Things (IoMusT)—has ushered in a new era of creative, educational and interactive possibilities. This literature review has explored a diverse range of applications, from real-time collaborative performances and smart music education platforms to AI-enhanced feature extraction and secure streaming environments.

IoT technologies are enabling musical instruments and systems to become more responsive, intelligent and connected. Through the support of enabling infrastructures such as 5G, edge computing, artificial intelligence and blockchain, IoMusT applications are now capable of supporting immersive learning, personalized music recommendations, emotion-aware interaction and low-latency remote performance. Another emerging area of interest is the lifecycle management of IoMusT systems. This includes the recyclability of smart instruments, modular upgrades to reduce electronic waste and support for repairability. As IoT devices proliferate in musical contexts, integrating circular economy principles into design and deployment will become increasingly important.

However, alongside these opportunities lie a number of challenges. Latency, interoperability, security, energy consumption and research integrity continue to pose barriers to broader adoption and long-term sustainability. In response, researchers are now actively developing green IoT strategies, decentralized music ecosystems and digital twin simulations to address these issues and push the boundaries of what IoT can offer to the musical world.

Emerging trends such as Musical XR, biometric feedback in education and blockchain-based copyright systems suggest a future in which music is not only a form of art and entertainment but also a smart, adaptive and deeply interconnected experience. To realize this potential, future research should continue to prioritize interdisciplinary collaboration, ethical innovation and open standards, ensuring that IoT-driven music technologies remain inclusive, secure and creatively empowering. Interdisciplinary partnerships between engineers, musicians, educators and sustainability experts are vital for developing IoMusT systems that are not only technically robust, but also culturally meaningful and environmentally responsible

In conclusion, IoT integration in music is evolving into a complex and vibrant field that blends creativity with connectivity. By understanding the structure and dynamics of current research, scholars, practitioners and professionals can better navigate the opportunities and challenges of the Internet of Musical Things.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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